

TABLE 2—IR AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE CYANOPYRIDINES (2)

Sl. no.*	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)		δ (CDCl ₃)					
	NH ₂	C≡N (conj)	OH ₂	OCH ₃	≡OH	NH ₂	ArH (R ¹)	ArH (R)
1.	3 440, 3 300, 3 160	2 220s	—	—	7.15(s)	7.25–7.55(bs)	7.72(s)	7.0(s)
2.	3 445, 3 315, 3 170	2 220s	2.48s	—	7.9(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.25(s)	7.8–8.2(d)
3.	3 450, 3 340, 3 140	2 220s	—	3.85s	7.18(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	6.9–7.1(d)	7.9–8.1(d)
4.	3 470, 3 370, 3 140	2 220s	—	—	7.98(s)	7.5–7.8(bs)	7.28(s)	7.9–8.2(d)
5.	3 480, 3 375, 3 155	2 220s	—	—	7.9(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.2(s)	7.75–8.2(d)
6.	3 440, 3 320, 3 160	2 220s	—	—	7.2(s)	7.5–7.65(bs)	6.8–7.1(d)	7.82–8.3(d)
7.	3 465, 3 365, 3 155	2 220s	—	—	7.82(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.25(s)	7.75–8.3(d)
8.	3 450, 3 355, 3 145	2 220s	—	—	7.84(s)	7.5–7.82(bs)	7.0–7.2(s)	7.85–8.25(d)
9.	3 470, 3 365, 3 140	2 220s	—	—	7.84(s)	7.5–7.8(bs)	7.25(s)	7.85–8.2(d)

*Compd. refers as in Table 1.

Scheme 1

proton (pyridine nucleus) at δ 7.15–7.38, NH₂ protons as a broad singlet at δ 7.25–7.82, aromatic protons-(R¹) at δ 6.8–7.28, aromatic protons-(R) at δ 7.0–8.3, CH₂ protons as a sharp singlet at δ 2.48 and OCH₃ protons as a sharp singlet at δ 3.85 ppm. The ir and nmr spectral data of the cyanopyridines are recorded in Table 2.

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Antimicrobial Study of some Indole Derivatives

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INDOLE derivatives show marked biological properties¹. Hydrazine derivatives² are potent inhibitors of monoamineoxidase enzyme, showing appreciable anticonvulsant activity. Reports reveal that substituted-malonanilic acid hydrazides are biologically important.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and antimicrobial studies of some indole-3-carboxaldehyde malonanilic acid hydrazones (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their counter synthesis, and elemental analysis, m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

The ir spectra of the compounds revealed $\nu_{\max}$ 1 650, 1 600 and 1 490 (C=O), 1 420 and 1 240 (C-N), 1 330 (Ar-N) and 750 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted benzene ring); $\lambda_{\max}$ 331.5 and 293.5 nm, supporting the validity of the compounds.

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde: It was prepared by the reported method⁸.

Malonanilic acid hydrazides: Malonanilic acid hydrazides were prepared in two stages⁴. The amine and diethylmalonate were mixed and heated for 1 h, then cooled and ethanol was added. To the separated ethyl malonanilate dissolved in ethanol, was added hydrazine hydrate (99%) dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture was set aside for 1 h and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol.

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde malonanilic acid hydrazone: A mixture of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) and malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 4 h in ethanol (50 ml). The contents were then cooled, filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	228	70.81
2.	2-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₂	264	71.98
3.	3-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₂	211	69.11
4.	4-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₂	152	70.52
5.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄	201	73.97
6.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄	215	71.23
7.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄	178	69.86
8.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	210	71.42
9.	3-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	140	67.14
10.	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	185	74.28
11.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	135	70.05
12.	3-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	218	73.35
13.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	270	70.35
14.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	252	71.85
15.	3,4-(OH) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	205	70.40

Biological screening: The compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antitubercular activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *In vitro* antitubercular activity was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *M. tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The retardation of growth was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The antibacterial activity was tested by cup-plate method⁶ using a species of gram (+ve) bacteria *S. aureus* and gram (-ve) bacteria *E. coli* in DMF.

Results and Discussion

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde substituted malonanilic acid hydrazones were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compounds with 3-chloro, 4-chloro, 4-nitro, 3-methoxy, 4-ethoxy, 2-methyl, 4-methyl and 3,4-dimethyl substitution to phenyl ring were active against *S. aureus*. Out of 15 compounds, 8 compounds were active against *S. aureus*, and out of 15 compounds, 5 compounds were active against *E. coli*. Compounds with 3-nitro, 4-methoxy, 3-methyl, 4-methyl and without substitution to phenyl ring were more active against *S. aureus* than *E. coli*. The same compounds when tested for their antitubercular activity, 4-chloro, 4-nitro, 4-methoxy, 4-ethoxy, 4-methyl and 3,4-dimethylphenyl derivatives were found active.

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Studies in Synthesis of Amidoxime. Synthesis of Hexahydro-2H-azepin-2-one Oxime

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REACTION between the carbonyl compounds and hydroxylamine or its salts are known as oximation reactions which have been thoroughly studied and the quantitative methods based on